

ERRATUM

Citation: Winterbottom, R., Erdmann, M.V. & Mambrasar, R. (2019) A new species of *Trimma* (Teleostei: Gobiidae) from Indonesia and Timor-Leste. *Journal of the Ocean Science Foundation*, 32, 47–55.

The holotype specimen of *Trimma putrai* Winterbottom, Erdmann & Mambrasar, 2019 has been deposited at the Museum Zoologicum Bogoriense, Cibinong, Java, Indonesia (MZB).

***Trimma putrai*, n. sp.**

Holotype. MZB 24001, 20.4 mm SL, male, Indonesia, West Papua, Raja Ampat Islands, Batanta, -0.9133°, 130.5584°, 35 m, clove oil, M.V. Erdmann, 18 February 2012.

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